

Original Research Article

Phytochemical and Antimicrobial Activity Screening of Some Liquid Herbal Products Sold in Suleja, Niger State, Nigeria

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Abstract

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There are several hundreds of plants that are identified reasonable sources of medicinal agents which dated back to the age long history of mankind globally. The aim of this research is to examine the antimicrobial potential and the phytochemicals present in liquid herbal products. Fifteen (15) liquid herbal products hawked were randomly purchased from herbal medicine vendors in the streets and markets in Suleja, Niger State, Nigeria. The samples were coded as SHM, SHBA, LHM, GHHP, NG, MS, MM, FGBE, TM, GI, FM, GEI, GHCR, GHC and AIHMC. These products were qualitatively screened for phytochemical constituents and antimicrobial potentials using standard methods. The results of phytochemicals revealed the presence of phenols, saponins, flavonoids, alkaloids, cardiac glycosides, anthraquinones and carbohydrates. The herbal products (MS and GI) at the stock concentrations (50.00 mg/mL) had activity against most of the bacteria and fungus with zones of inhibition ranging from 11- 20 mm. While herbal products (SHBA, LHM, GHHP and GEI) at 50mg/mL had activity against four of the test microorganisms. Two of the herbal products (FM and GHC) had activity against one microorganism. The herbal products had varied antimicrobial activity to justify the continue use to treat the said ailments. The study identified the presence of phytochemicals that possess the antimicrobial property of some of the herbal products.

Keywords: Antimicrobial potential, Liquid herbal products, Phytochemical, Qualitatively screened, Stock concentrations, Suleja

INTRODUCTION

There are several hundreds of plants that are identified reasonable sources of medicinal agents which dated back to the age long history of mankind globally. Before the coming of orthodox medicine, most people depend totally on the use of traditional or locally herbs means for all their healthcare needs, these include the use of plants and its products (herbal), mineral based herbal medicines and animal often laced with spiritual ingredients such as incantations (Mbotu et al., 2009; Faza and Sngh, 2015).

These plants are used by traditional medicine healers for numerous different purposes, including bacterial, viral, fungal and other infections (Obafemi et al., 2006). These infectious diseases may be an inevitable fact of life, however, there are several strategies available to aid us protect ourselves from such infections and to treat a disease once it has evolved (Rajkumar et al., 2017). Now the control of microbial activity through the active properties of naturally occurring constituents has become

a vital research area (Rajkumar et al., 2017). Therefore, the search for effective plants and plant constituents against these pathogenic microorganisms has become increasingly important outcome of the development of antibiotic resistance in microbes (Ahmad et al., 2006). Nowadays, researchers are looking at a broad range of indigenous medicinal plants for antimicrobial action principles that have little or no side effects (Chandra et al., 2017).

Also, resistances of most microorganism especially bacteria have been increased due to random use of synthetic or commercial antimicrobial medicines mostly used in the treatment of infectious diseases (Penesyany et al., 2015). These circumstances forced researchers to probe for new antimicrobial and therapeutic substances from other sources, such as plants of medicinal importance (Karaman et al., 2003). There are several published documents that have shown the effectiveness of traditional herbs against many microorganisms of public health significance (Ahmad et al., 2006; Obafemi et al., 2006; Mboto et al., 2009; Faza and Singh, 2015; Penesyany et al., 2015; Rajkumar et al., 2017). As a consequence, plants are one of the building blocks for modern medicines to achieve the desired new principles (Evans et al., 2002).

The medicinal worth of these plants lies in some chemical and therapeutic substances that produce a definite physiological action on the human body. These plants are capable of producing an incredible array of secondary metabolites which can be developed into economically important products including; oils, gums, resins, flavonoids, phenolic compounds, tannins, rubber, waxes, pigments, flavors, alkaloids, fragrances, surfactants, preservatives, pesticides, and other pharmaceuticals important sources (Singh et al., 2011). Therefore, plants of medicinal values are under tremendous pressure across the globe, especially in Nigeria, to commercialize into phytomedicines for management of ailments. The World Health Organization (WHO) survey report estimates that approximately four million people (about 70-80% of the global population) depend on non-conventional medicines that are mainly of herbal origins for their primary healthcare (Ampofo et al., 2012).

The plants and plants products may also give a new source of antimicrobial agents with the possibly novel mechanism of action compare to the synthetic drugs. Scientists reported that antimicrobial of plant origin are not associated with several side effects and have an enormous therapeutic potential to heal many infectious diseases (Abo et al., 2006). The use of traditional medicine among the tribal local people and medicinal healers in developing countries is widely practiced till date (Rajkumar et al., 2017). However, medicinal quality of plants depends on their chemical constituents that have physiological activity in human systems (Kumar et al., 2009). Thus, it is of paramount important to determine

antimicrobial of plant extracts and phytochemicals, since they form the basis for antimicrobial drug discovery (Cseke et al., 2006).

In Nigeria, the number of advertised, marked and widely used herbal preparations with spurious claim to combat all sort of human ailments is at alarming rate. This is very worrisome as herbal preparations are admixture of complex plant materials which may contain potentially toxic substances. In addition, the concentration, dosage, shelf life and microbiological quality of some of the locally used herbal products are uncertain and possess fake NAFDAC registration identity (Oyetayo, 2008). The above points are in contrast to the embargo of the manufacture, advertisement, sales, distributions and consumption of herbal medicinal products in Nigeria without due and proper registration by National Agency for Food and Drug Administration and Control (NAFDAC) (HMRPRR, 2004). The European Agency for the Evaluation of Medicinal Products (EMA) and World Health Organization (WHO) has spelled out that the amount of the herbal preparation should be given within the range corresponding to a described amount of composition with well-known therapeutic activity. However, if the constituent(s) responsible for the therapeutic activity are unknown, the quantity of the whole herbal drug preparation should be given (WHO, 1996; EMA, 2003).

In a previous study, the phytochemical and antibacterial evaluation of selected locally produced herbal medicines sold in Calabar, Nigeria was determined and showed the presences of alkaloids and Cardiac glycosides (Agbo and Mboto, 2012). However, there is a need to evaluate the phytochemicals and antimicrobial of liquid herbal products hawked at Suleja, Niger State, Nigeria. Therefore, the aim of this research is to examine the antimicrobial potential and phytochemicals present in some liquid herbal products hawked at Suleja, Niger State, Nigeria.

The phytochemical screening of the herbal medicines showed reducing compounds and polyphenol to be present in much excess amount (+++) in 50% and 30% of the sampled herbal medicines respectively were present in excess amount (++) in 70% of the herbal medicines. were present (+) in 90% of the herbal medicines sampled, while saponin was absent (-) in 80% of the herbal medicines sampled.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area

Suleja is a town in Suleja Local Government Area of Niger State. It is laying on latitude 7°11' E and longitude 9° 11' N with a population estimate of about 216, 578. Suleja, the headquarter of Suleja Emirate Council and sometimes confused with the nearby city of Abuja due to

its proximity and the facts that it was originally called Abuja before the Nigeria government adopted the name for its new Federal Capital Territory in 1976 (NPC, 2008).

Collection of Herbal Products

A total of fifteen (15) liquid herbal products of different manufacturer's marketed in Suleja were randomly selected and purchased for the investigation. These samples were coded as follow: SHM, SHBA, LHM, GHHP, NG, MS, MM, FGBE, TM, GI, FM, GEI, GHCR, GHC and AIHMC and stored at 4°C until used.

Macroscopic Examination of Herbal Products

The odour, colour, visibility, taste and other macroscopic examination was done on the collected liquid herbal medicine products.

Preparation of Herbal Products

The purchased liquid herbal products were concentrated on the water bath for seven (7) days to obtain various extracts and properly labeled until needed for use.

Phytochemical Screening of Liquid Herbal Products

The fifteen (15) liquid herbal products were screened qualitatively for the presence of alkaloids, phenols, cardiac glycosides, saponins, flavonoids, carbohydrates and anthraquinones, using standard methods as described by (Sofowora, 1994; Egawaikhide and Gimba, 2007; Gafar et al., 2010).

Antimicrobial Screening of the Herbal Extracts

The Test Isolates

The microorganisms used for the study were *Streptococcus pyogenes*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Salmonella paratyphi*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Escherichia coli* and *Candida albicans*. All the organisms used were clinical isolates obtained from the Department of Microbiology and Biotechnology, National Institute for Pharmaceutical Research and Development (NIPRD) Abuja. The bacteria were maintained on Muller Hinton Agar slant at 37°C and *Candida albicans* was maintained on potato dextrose agar slant at 30°C.

Preparation of Inoculums

A loop full each of the test microorganisms was inoculated into 4 ml sterile Mueller-Hinton Broth (MHB) for bacteria and Sabouraud Dextrose Broth (SDB) for fungi and incubated at 37°C for 2hrs. The turbidity of actively growing microbial suspension was adjusted with freshly prepared MHB and SDB using BaSO₄ turbidity standard to match turbidity standard of 0.5 McFarland. This turbidity obtained was equivalent to approximately 1.5x10⁸ CFU/mL cells for bacteria, and 1.5x10⁷ spores/mL for fungal strain. The growth suspension was used for further testing.

Preparation of the crude extracts

The extracts were prepared by weighing 0.2 g into sterile tubes and dissolved with 4 mL of sterile distilled water and vortexed for 5 minutes to get the stock solution of 50.00 mg/mL. From the stock solutions, two-fold dilutions were carried out to give the concentrations of 25.00, 12.50 and 6.25 mg/mL respectively (Raji et al., 2019).

Antimicrobial Screening

The antimicrobial assay of the extracts against the isolates was determined in the Department of Microbiology and Biotechnology, National Institute for Pharmaceutical Research and Development, using Kirby-Bauer agar diffusion method according to NCCLS standards (NCCLS, 2000). One hundred microliter (100µL) of the suspension of standardized microorganisms were inoculated into twenty-three millilitres (23mL) of sterilized molten MHA and SDA, properly mixed and poured into sterile petri dishes, swirled and allowed to set under aseptic condition. Holes for each concentration of the extracts and positive controls were bored aseptically using a sterile cork borer of 6 mm. The bottoms of the wells were sealed with a drop of MHA and SDA. Then, two hundred microlitres of different concentrations of the extracts and positive controls, Ofloxacin and Fluconazole being the drug of choice as a broad-spectrum antibiotic was dispensed into appropriately labeled wells respectively. The plates were left in the safety hood for 2 h for proper diffusion of the extracts into the agar and then incubated at 37°C for 24h for bacteria. The same procedure was repeated for fungi strain and incubated at 25°C for 48 h for fungi. The above procedures were duplicated for test bacteria and fungi followed by appropriate incubation. The plates were observed for antimicrobial activity by measuring the size of the zone of inhibition surrounding wells in vertical and horizontal direction and taking the average (mean) of the readings (Abdulmumin et al., 2019).

Table 1. Phytochemicals Profile of Liquid Herbal Products

S/N	Samples Codes	a	b	c	d	E	f	g
1	SHM	-	-	+	+	-	+	+
2	SHBA	-	-	-	+	+	-	+
3	LHM	-	+	-	+	+	-	+
4	GHHP	+	-	-	+	-	-	-
5	MS	-	-	-	+	+	-	+
6	NG	+	-	-	+	-	-	-
7	MM	-	+	-	-	-	-	-
8	FGBE	-	-	-	-	+	-	-
9	TM	+	+	+	+	+	+	-
10	GI	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
11	FM	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
12	GEI	-	+	-	-	-	-	+
13	GHCR	-	-	-	-	-	+	-
14	GHC	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
15	AIHMC	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Key: a = Phenols, b = Flavonoids, c = Cardiac glycosides, d = Anthraquinones, e = Alkaloids
f = Saponins, g = Carbohydrates, - = Negative, + = Positive.

Table 2. Zones of inhibition of test bacterial and fungal against extracts

S/N	SAMPLES	The isolates used/Zone of inhibition (mm) at 50 mg/mL							
		<i>S. pyogenes</i>	<i>K. pneumoniae</i>	<i>S. paratyphi</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>C. albicans</i>
01	SHM	-	16	-	-	-	-	-	15
02	SHBA	-	15	-	-	-	12	-	18
03	LHM	-	17	15	-	-	-	16	-
04	GHHP	18	14	17	-	-	-	-	-
05	NG	-	13	-	-	-	-	-	11
06	MS	17	11	18	20	-	15	-	16
07	MM	-	-	16	-	-	-	12	-
08	FGBE	14	-	-	-	11	-	-	-
09	TM	-	-	-	12	-	-	11	-
10	GI	12	14	14	-	12	11	-	-
11	FM	-	-	-	-	-	-	15	-
12	GEI	14	18	15	-	-	-	-	-
13	GHCR	-	-	14	-	-	16	-	-
14	GHC	-	-	-	-	-	13	-	-
15	AIHMC	-	-	-	13	-	-	15	-
16	Controls	27	24	28	29	23	21	25	27

RESULTS

The result of the qualitative phytochemical screening carried on liquid herbal products to determine the presence of medicinally important phytochemicals in the products revealed the presence of phenols, saponins, flavonoids, alkaloids, cardiac glycosides, anthraquinones and carbohydrates. The sample coded TM contains (85.7%) phytochemical constituents with absence of carbohydrate. Alkaloids present in samples coded SHBA, LHM, MS, NG, FGBE and TM. Anthraquinones, phenols, flavonoids, cardiac glycosides, saponins and carbohydrates are present in 46.7%, 20%, 26.7%, 13.3%, 20% and 40% respectively as shown in Table 1.

The inhibitory potentials of the liquid herbal products were screened and found effective against some clinical microbial strains as demonstrated in Table 2. Some of the liquid herbal products extracts exhibited inhibitory actions at the stock concentrations (50.00 mg/mL) against some test isolates with zones of inhibition ranging from 11-20 mm. The coded MS had growth inhibitions against six of test microorganisms (Table 2). GI extract inhibited the growth of five of the test microorganisms. The least liquid herbal product extract (GHC) inhibited the growth of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. The control drugs for the experiment (Ofloxacin (bacteria) and Fluconazole (fungus) showed reasonable antimicrobial potency against all the isolates.

DISCUSSION

The phytochemicals in the plants and its products has been utilized for several curative properties in animal and human medicine (Yadav et al., 2014). These secondary metabolites are also known to have contribute tremendously towards the biological actions of medicinal plants such as antioxidant, antifungal, antibacterial, antimalarial, anti-inflammatory, anticholinergic anticarcinogenic and antileprosy activities (Yadav et al., 2014), hence its application is well noticed and efficient in drug discovery and development. In this study, we examined qualitatively, the phytochemicals present in fifteen (15) liquid herbal products hawked in Suleja area of Niger State, Nigeria. The results revealed variety of phytochemicals present in the liquid herbal products. The findings of this study agree with a similar study that reported presence of some of these chemical compounds in these liquid herbal products screened and possess the same properties (Agbo and Mbotto, 2012).

In this study, some of the coded samples (SHBA, NG and TM) revealed the presence of alkaloids that can be exploited as potent antimicrobial agents. The flavonoids present (LHM, MM and GEI) and phenols (GHHP, NG and TM) in sample codes may act as scavengers of free radicals and are thus effective as anti-oxidative, anti-inflammatory and antibacterial agent. These are similar to the findings of some researchers who reported the significant of these chemical constituents in plants (Taylor and Hefle, 2017; Seriki et al., 2019). However, the excess of alkaloids in the human body could affect the central nervous system, reduces appetite and act as a diuretic. It may also act as protein and as body building components and blocks of life (Taylor and Hefle, 2017). This could also attribute to the antimicrobial potency of the liquid herbal product it possesses in this study of some samples.

The findings from this study also show the presence of flavonoids, that are proven by researchers can inhibit variety of cancers in animal, provided strong anti-proliferation effects against liver and colon cancer cells, reduced dangerous inflammation in the arteries, and may also have positive effects on blood clotting, coronary artery function and insulin sensitivity. (Seriki et al., 2019). Thus, taking or drinking some these products (LHM, NG, TM and GEI) coded samples can be use in resolving such cases.

This study also revealed the presence of saponin in some sample codes (SHM, TM and GHCR) which agrees with results of Picincu (2018) that reported presence of saponins of herbal products that are also proven to have the ability to improve immune function, reduce cholesterol levels, kill disease-causing bacteria, scavenge oxidative stress and inhibit tumour growth.

The presence of these vital phytochemical constituents in this study has shown that these products could be of great use in the pharmaceutical

industry in the development of drug and herbal remedies in nervous and cardiac disorders and others (Rajkumar et al., 2017). Therefore, effort put in place to authenticate the products of traditional medical practitioners who claimed to treat all manners of infectious ailments.

Fifteen (15) liquid herbal products extracts each had *in vitro* antimicrobial susceptibility assay was performed on *Streptococcus pyogenes*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Salmonella paratyphi*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Escherichia coli* and *Candida albicans*. The results revealed the inhibitory actions of some coded samples that are highly appreciated by showing different manners of inhibition of growths. All the herbal product extracts expressed activity on one organism or the other. The most susceptible isolate was *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, followed by *S. paratyphi*, *Streptococcus pyogenes* and *P. aeruginosa*, *Escherichia coli* and *Candida albicans* and then, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Bacillus subtilis*. These antimicrobial activities recorded in this study could be due to the active chemical constituents present in the herbal products.

Table 2 depicts the zones of inhibition of the liquid product extracts against the test microorganisms. The herbal extracts exhibited varied antimicrobial activity against the microorganisms. The zones of inhibition of these extracts were found to be lower than the gentamicin as control. This is expected because of the synthetic nature of gentamicin as pure compound. The coded (MS and GI) extracts had activity against six and five test microorganisms. Most of the herbal extracts (7) had activity against two test microorganism and the least of the extracts (GHC and FM) had activity on one test microorganism. The finding of this study revealed that the herbal products inhibited the growths of *P. aeruginosa*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Salmonella paratyphi*, *Streptococcus pyogenes* and *Candida albicans* especially (MS). The results agree with similar works of other researchers (Anyaocha et al., 2016; Ikeghunam et al., 2012; Nwankwo et al., 2012) that reported herbal mixtures inhibited the growths of *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumonia*, *Salmonella* spp and *Candida albicans*. The study also differed from other works that reported that some of the herbal products do not have any antimicrobial activity (Oyetayo, 2008; Anyaocha et al., 2016; Ngemenya et al., 2019).

Inflammation of respiratory tract which is cause by *Pseudomonas* spp and typhoid fever caused by *Salmonella* spp are often difficult to combat (Abdullahi et al., 2012), but the growths of these organisms were greatly challenged by some of herbal remedies. *E. coli* is implicated as the etiological agent of gastro-intestinal and also causes infections in the lungs especially in immunocompromised persons (Black, 1996). The isolates used in this study also showed some level of susceptibility to some of the extracts of the herbal products. Thus, the activities observed from some of the

herbal remedies suggested that some of the remedies may be sufficiently potent against the clinical infectious ailments.

However, in this study, when the zones of inhibition of each extract were compared with the standard drugs, it was observed that the positive controls are more active than herbal extracts. The findings of this study revealed that all the herbal products analyzed for antimicrobial activity justified the claims of use in the treatment of respiratory tract and gastroenteritis related diseases.

CONCLUSION

From the above findings in this study, the liquid herbal products have shown potentials for phyto-therapeutic management of tropical diseases. Further studies on these herbal products should be considered in order to isolate, identify, characterize and elucidate the structure of the bioactive compounds. Microbiological quality assessment of herbal products is also an important step toward improvement of the herbal products for better ethnomedicinal uses in Nigeria.

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